

Teacher Change in Classroom Management: A Mixed-Method Study with Vocational Teachers

Abstract

Classroom management has a major impact on students' motivation and learning outcomes. However, studies are needed to understand why teachers adopt/discard those instructional practices and how the process of changes in practice takes place. Using a mixed-method design, we investigated whether and how classroom management-related beliefs and self-reported practices change over the first year of teacher education. Results revealed that teacher education has important implications for classroom management beliefs and practices: Teachers moved toward beliefs and practices encouraged by the teacher education program. Surveys and interviews indicated that changes in practices strongly depend on teachers' beliefs. Changes were affected by the school context, specifically the alignment between the values conveyed by the teacher education program and those of the schools.

Introduction

Research has shown that instructional practices, notably classroom management, have a significant impact on students' motivation and, thus, on learning outcomes. For instance, students of an autonomy-supportive and structuring teacher tend to be more intrinsically motivated and, thus, cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally more engaged in learning than students of a controlling teacher (Deci, Schwartz, Sheinman, & Ryan, 1981; Jang, Reeve, & Deci, 2010; Kunter, Baumert, & Köller, 2007).

While extensive research has been conducted regarding which practices encourage student engagement and how engagement occurs (Reeve, 2009; Turner et al., 2014), further studies are needed to explain why teachers adopt or discard those instructional practices and how the process of changes in practice takes place. Such an explanation might come from research indicating that beliefs are critical in defining behavior and organizing knowledge; in this view, instructional practices are assumed to be grounded in teachers' beliefs (Buehl & Beck, 2015; Pajares, 1992). Beliefs can be subject to change and are expected to evolve notably with teacher education. Indeed, teacher education aims to guide teachers toward practices and beliefs that favor student engagement and learning.

However it is important to adopt a broader perspective, considering not only what happens during teacher education but also other teaching and learning experiences; these include teaching experiences before entering teacher education and experiences obtained in

the schools in which teachers are employed.¹ Accordingly, the present mixed-methods study aimed to investigate not only *if* and *how* teachers change, but *why* they change. The participants were teachers in vocational school in Switzerland who were following teacher education and teaching classes concurrently. The goals of this study were the following:

- 1) Assess (quantitatively) whether and how *classroom management-related beliefs and self-reported practices* change over the first year of teacher education;
- 2) Investigate, using both quantitative and qualitative analyses, the factors that might explain the changes.

Theoretical Framework

Beliefs are grounded in subjective evaluations and judgments, and they are critical in explaining teachers' ways of thinking, understanding, and behaving (Nespor, 1987; Pajares, 1992). By the time teachers enter teacher education, their beliefs are well established (Lortie, 1975). One of the challenges of teacher education is to have teachers examine their beliefs in order to foster more favorable instructional practices. Studies have shown that teacher education can impact beliefs and practices. For instance, Shalter Bruening (2010) showed that teacher education significantly impacted teachers' beliefs about student motivation. However, other studies indicate that prior beliefs are resistant to change (Huberman, 1973; Turner, 2010), and that teacher education has a limited impact on them (Mansfield & Volet, 2010; Richardson & Placier, 2001). This resistance to change may be caused by prior beliefs that act as filters to insulate teachers from the beneficial impact of teacher education. Accordingly, it is important to determine the role of such factors and of those that facilitate change such as sharing opportunities with significant others (Kagan, 1992) or the teaching context of the school in which teachers are employed (Pelletier, Séguin-Lévesque, & Legault, 2002).

To address changes in teachers' classroom management practices and beliefs, vocational teachers were surveyed on two occasions and then interviewed. Our assessment of practices was based on a framework (Reeve, Deci, & Ryan, 2004) of two opposing continua of instructional practices or classroom management styles: Autonomy support versus control, and structure versus chaos. Autonomy-supportive teachers listen to their students' expressions and needs, encourage students to find answers by themselves, and encourage students' intrinsic motivation. Controlling teachers favor extrinsic motivational resources, use coercive language, express judgments, and position themselves as dominant. Structure refers to the

¹ In Switzerland, vocational teachers (including the participants in this study) start teaching in a vocational school some years before entering teacher education. They continue teaching during the teacher education program.

quantity and clarity of teachers' information and expectations (Skinner & Belmont, 1993). Structuring practices involve providing clear information and rationales for activities. Chaos is the opposite: Teachers give confusing information and expectations. (Skinner, Furrer, Marchand, & Kindermann, 2008). Research has shown that an optimal classroom management style combines autonomy, support, and structure (Jang et al., 2010).

We focused on two types of beliefs about teaching and learning: general pedagogical beliefs and beliefs about student motivation. General pedagogical beliefs refer to teachers' conceptions about the efficiency of teaching behaviors and students' learning strategies (Chan & Elliot, 2004). A basic distinction is made between the conception of teaching as a mere transmission of knowledge to students (direct transmission) and the belief that a good teacher should focus on students and favor their active learning (constructivism). Student-centered beliefs, such as constructivism, are linked to student-oriented practices, such as supporting students' autonomy. Likewise, teacher-centered beliefs, such as direct transmission, are connected to teacher-oriented practices, such as controlling practices (Chen, Brown, Hattie, & Millward, 2012).

Beliefs about student motivation fall into two broad categories: belief in using intrinsic forms of motivation (e.g., considering students' interests) and belief in using extrinsic motivation (e.g., rewards, threats). The more teachers believe in the utility of fostering intrinsic motivation, the more they support students' autonomy (Reeve, 2009).

Most generally, we predicted that teachers' beliefs and practices would evolve toward those encouraged by the teacher education program (constructivism, autonomy support, and structure) and their school context (Reeve et al., 2004; Shalter Bruening, 2010). This context may or may not foster the same value as the teacher education program. We expected this evolution of practices to be accompanied by changes in teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning (Chen et al., 2012; Reeve, 2009).

Method

Survey

Forty-seven vocational teachers in Switzerland's French-speaking region participated in the study. Their teacher education was occurring alongside their teaching jobs. The participants' mean teaching experience prior to entering education was three years. They completed a survey on two occasions: once at the onset of teacher education (T1) and again nine months later, at the end of the first year of teacher education (T2). The survey included measures of *classroom management self-reported practices*, *general pedagogical beliefs*, and *beliefs about student motivation* (see Table 1 for sample items and internal consistency).

Our measurement of *classroom management self-reported practices*, inspired by the “Problem in School Questionnaire” (Deci et al., 1981), consisted of six vignettes describing typical problematic classroom situations during class. Each vignette was followed by four sentences mirroring four types of classroom management practices described above. To assess *general pedagogical beliefs*, 12 items were adapted from the OECD Teaching and Learning International Study (Berger, J.-L., 2012; Jensen, Sandoval-Hernandez, Knoll, & Gonzalez, 2012). Finally, *beliefs about how to motivate students* were measured by 12 items translated and adapted from various scales assessing the perceived utility of methods to foster student motivation (Nolen & Nicholls, 1994; Shalter Bruening, 2010; Stipek, Givvin, Salmon, & M

Interviews

Using latent change scores, we selected 17 participants for semi-structured interviews revolving around the evolution of their classroom management since they started teaching. Nine participants showed a change in their practices toward more autonomy support and structure, while the other eight seemed to have resisted change during that year. After reflecting on their present practices, we asked them to pick a very similar situation that happened at the start of their teaching career and to explain their reaction back then. Finally, we asked them to reflect on the evolution (or lack of evolution) of their practices and on the factors that, in their opinion, impacted this evolution.

This presentation focuses on four case studies to describe opposing views on classroom management. For illustrative purposes, we chose two participants for each category (change versus resistance) inferred from the survey. In each pair, one showed strong coherence in their survey and interview responses while the other showed significant incoherence. A brief description of the four participants who took part in the interviews is provided in Table 2. Data analysis followed an iterative process of content analysis and coding development, using inputs from the literature on the impact of teacher education on teachers’ evolution of teaching practices and beliefs. All the data were coded by the first author according to a coding scheme developed by the two authors in a prior study (Girardet, C., & Berger, J.L., submitted for publication).

Results

Analyses of the mean differences, using repeated measures ANOVA (see Table 1), revealed a significant ($p < .05$) increase in teachers’ autonomy support and constructivist beliefs and a significant decrease in control, structure, direct transmission beliefs and beliefs in the utility of promoting extrinsic motivation. Correlations between these changes revealed connections between the evolution of beliefs and that of practices (a) between the evolutions of controlling

practices and beliefs in direct transmission ($r(45) = .33, p < .05$) and (b) between autonomy-support and constructivism ($r(45) = .46, p < .01$).

This alignment between beliefs and practices was also reflected in the interviews. Teacher education made one of the teachers (Brigitte) aware of the importance of considering learners' individual characteristics and needs: a facet of constructivism. She adapted her practices accordingly, offering students opportunities to study in conditions that suited their needs (e.g., listening to music, working in groups). Another's (Mathieu's) beliefs were also aligned to his practices by relying on extrinsic motivation: "The one who finds the correct answer, I'll give him a piece of chocolate, or something like that" (Mathieu). He justified this by observing that it actually worked (students engage in learning). Mathieu thus believed in the use of extrinsic motivation to foster student engagement and favored controlling practices over autonomy-supportive ones.

Analyzing the interviews allowed us to identify three main "trigger" factors that played an important role in the evolution of instructional practices: teacher education, significant others, and personal factors. Teacher education factors included specific classes, learning activities, inspiring teacher educators, and teacher educators' visits to the teachers' classrooms. Significant others refer to colleagues, peers, friends, teacher educators, and the school's director: whomever the teacher interacted with and was significantly influenced by. This result corroborates previous research demonstrating that sharing opportunities helps teachers reflect on their teaching and facilitates their professional development (Kagan, 1992). Finally, personal factors refer to class events, difficult students, or trials of new practices.

Those triggers bring teachers knowledge, but the way teachers process and enact these elements can be influenced by the school context, which can facilitate or impede the evolution of a teacher's belief system. Unlike one of the teachers (Aurélien), whose constructivist beliefs were consistent with her school's values, Brigitte felt that her student-centered beliefs were not supported. This lack of alignment between Brigitte's beliefs and her school's values prevented her, at first, from being as autonomy-supportive as she wanted to be. Teacher education enabled her to work on her self-confidence, which helped her to justify her instructional practices to her more traditional and unsupportive colleagues. Along with further analysis of teacher change, the poster presentation will provide considerations on how and why results from the survey and the interview are concordant or discordant.

Significance of the Study

This study revealed that teacher education has important implications for classroom management beliefs and practices: Except for the decrease in structuring practices, teachers moved toward beliefs and practices that were encouraged by the teacher education program. Furthermore, indications were found in the surveys and the interviews that changes in practices are strongly dependent on teachers' beliefs. Changes in teachers' practices were affected by their school context, particularly by the degree of alignment between the values conveyed by the teacher education program and those of the teachers' schools. Finally, the use of mixed methods provided deeper insight into dynamic nature of these influences.

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APPENDIX

Scale	Sample item	# Items	Range	T1			T2			F	p	η^2_p
				M	SD	α	M	SD	α			
<i>Self-reported classroom management practices</i>												
<i>Vignette: "It has been two weeks that a student appears listless and disengaged from your class. His work is correct but he has not been completing assignments. Your reaction would be to:"</i>												
Autonomy-support	Try to help him determine the source of his disengagement.	6	1-7	5.20	0.74	.60	5.57	0.70	.70	11.79	<.001	.21
Structure	Remind him of the reasons why schoolwork and active participation are important for his future.	6	1-7	5.43	0.81	.65	4.98	0.72	.47	13.43	<.001	.23
Control	Demand that he takes part in after class studies or tutoring classes.	6	1-7	2.85	1.13	.78	2.48	0.92	.77	10.83	.002	.20
Chaos	Wait until he gets bad grades and reacts on his own.	6	1-7	2.66	0.84	.64	2.60	0.84	.67	0.17	.679	-
<i>General pedagogical beliefs</i>												
Direct transmission	Frontal teaching is the most useful way to teach because it enables a teacher to provide students with more knowledge and information.	5	1-6	3.67	0.71	.67	3.30	0.71	.61	26.03	<.001	.36
Constructivism	A good teacher encourages students to think of answers and solutions by themselves.	6	1-6	4.76	0.61	.69	4.99	0.54	.73	4.82	.033	.10
<i>Beliefs about how to motivate students</i>												
Promoting intrinsic motivation	It is useful to take into account students' interests to motivate them.	4	1-6	4.99	0.50	.60	4.98	0.50	.66	.02	.901	-
Promoting extrinsic motivation	To motivate students, it is useful to remind them that they might get bad grades if they do not study enough.	4	1-6	3.23	0.83	.75	2.94	0.85	.81	9.02	.004	.16

Note. α = Cronbach's alpha

Table 2. *Interview participants' characteristics.*

Pseudo	Sex	Age	Subject taught	Teaching experience	T1-T2 type of change	Interview perceived change
Aurélie	F	43	Information and communication	2	Change toward more autonomy-support and structure	Similar to change observed in the survey
Mathieu	M	37	Carpentry	1	Change toward more autonomy-support and structure	Lack of change
Brigitte	F	33	Arts	5	Lack of change	Change toward more autonomy-support and structure
Antoine	M	27	Mechanics	1	Lack of change	Similar to (lack of) change observed in the survey